

THE EFFICIENCY OF LANGUAGE LEARNING THROUGH EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES

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ABSTRACT

Hence, it is advisable for the student to respond briefly with two or three sentences and structure their queries in a way that facilitates the flow of the conversation. During the initial round, questions should pertain to two or three topics. The judges take turns asking questions or initiating discussions with the audience on any subject. In the second task of Round I, participants are required to describe one of the pictures they have previously created in class or at home. The six to eight conversational topics and pictures recommended for description in the competition will be announced to students in advance during the preparation period. For rounds II-III, the teacher should prepare an audio recording of texts. The contestants listen to the recording together with the teacher to engage in text-based conversations. The texts may be played multiple times at the discretion of the judges.

The number of times a reader listens to a text depends on their level of knowledge and language preparation. The texts for the second and third rounds of the competition are different from each other. In Round II, students listen to a text that is similar to what they studied in the previous class. The content of the text is closely related to one of the conversational topics that students have previously studied in the classroom. For the third round, the content of the texts should be completely new to the readers, but the lexical and grammatical constructions they encounter should not be a problem for the course participants. The pictures selected for the second and third rounds should be relevant to the conversational topics previously studied in the classroom, but new to the students. In the third round, the contestants will inscribe the dialogue of the characters in pairs, with five to six minutes given to prepare for the task. The best art word master and translator contests can also be held. The successful conduct of any competition or Olympiad depends on their thorough preparation and the precise organization of their holding. It is therefore important to consider their recording in order to analyze and evaluate students' responses. Various tools can be used to achieve this goal.

Although mass forms of extracurricular activities can be valuable and useful, they can be limited as the events are often repetitive and have short durations. To develop speech skills and abilities, regular practice and a consistent speech attitude are necessary. Thus, mass forms of extracurricular activities alone cannot solve the problem of speech development. Instead, permanent foreign language clubs should supplement public forms of work that are held from time to time. The circle is a common form of organizing extracurricular activities for foreign language programs. It is in these clubs that students typically prepare for public events. Therefore, foreign language teachers should organize clubs in every school, and enrollment should be voluntary with a limited number of participants. Advanced teachers suggest that classes in clubs should be held at least once every two weeks for 1-1.5 academic hours. The teacher determines the type and theme of the club based on the needs, interests, skills, and abilities of the students. Circles are organized for students of parallel classes to ensure that they can choose language material that is interesting and understandable. Foreign language clubs are divided into several types depending on the content of the course, including speech circles and speaking clubs, among others, which can be recommended for working with students at all stages of reading.

The teacher can organize various circles for high school students such as drama, literary translation, extracurricular reading, and country studies. Students in the higher levels of extracurricular reading and ethnography studies are interested and enthusiastic, while the play circle is popular among students in the lower levels of reading. The teacher should make sure that the students are always in a language environment by addressing each other and the teacher only in a foreign language. The success of the circles depends on skillful and purposeful planning, taking into account the skills and competencies that will be included in the lessons, such as monologue and dialogic speech and listening comprehension. The teacher can use various materials such as adapted or original texts, audio CDs, pictures, albums, and movies to develop the students' skills and abilities in any type of speech activity. Each topic can serve to develop a specific type of speech activity, and the teacher should choose materials that are most effective for developing the desired skills.

The teacher may assign individual tasks to gifted students. The teacher also considers how the skills and competencies learned in the club can be applied to the students' creative work outside of the club, particularly at public events. Both group work in foreign languages and circle work require individual attention and work with each participant. For example, the teacher should work individually with each performer to practice correct pronunciation and intonation for a small play in a foreign language. The teacher should also work separately with each participant in a literary montage in a foreign language. The teacher can help students prepare for a presentation in a foreign language by selecting appropriate literature and reviewing the report in advance to correct any errors. Individual forms of teacher work are also used to guide students who are particularly interested in learning a foreign language and reading foreign language literature.

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